

MEASUREMENT SYSTEM FOR INPUT BIAS –OFFSET CURRENTS OF AN OPERATIONAL AMPLIFIER

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ABSTRACT

A very simple microprocessor (μP) -based dedicated instrument is designed here. The Overall system design consists of both hardware and software designs. This set-up yields the exact values of input bias and input off-set currents on the μP display panel, one after the other, when the operational amplifier (OP- AMP) under test is connected across the test terminals.

KEYWORDS Microprocessor 8088, Programmable Interface Adapter, Analogue-to-Digital Converter, Input Offset Current, Input Bias Current, OP-AMP, Signal Conditioner, High Accuracy, Assembly Language Programming.

INTRODUCTION

With advances in solid state technology, op-amps have become highly reliable, miniaturised and consistently predictable in performance. They are designed to handle analogue signals which carry information in terms of amplitude and wave shape. For designing a circuit containing an op-amp, it is necessary to have the information regarding its parameters. However, the facility for measuring the parameters of linear op-amp (for DC Analysis) in a single instrument is not available indigenously. In this paper, an attempt has been made to determine two of the important parameters, i.e., input bias and offset currents respectively of an op-amp using microprocessor techniques. Although these currents are quite small, but even little deviation from zero results in wide variation in the output voltage. A little mismatch between the input stages of an op-amp causes unequal bias currents flowing into two inputs and it results in the input off-set current not being zero. This is contrary to the basic assumption in circuit analysis.

BASIC INTERNAL STRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF AN OP-AMP

An OP-AMP is a DC amplifier having a high gain, of the order of 10^4 to 10^8 . Such an amplifier can perform summing, integration, differentiation, or act as comparator with suitable feedback networks.

The block diagram of an OP-AMP, shown in Fig.1, consists of a four-stage direct-coupled amplifier in cascade.

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of an OP-AMP

Overall gain (or overall amplification) = $M_{IN} \times M_{INT} \times M_O$ (very high).

The first input stage is a double-ended high-gain differential amplifier. The intermediate stage is a single-ended differential amplifier. The third stage is a level shifter which is used as an emitter follower circuit.

The final stage is a push-pull complementary amplifier. With low output impedance and minimum offset voltage and currents the power gain ranges from 5 to 20 for this output stage.

An ideal OP-AMP exhibits the following electrical characteristics (Towers, et al, 2006):

- 1) Infinite voltage gain. That is, $A_v = \infty$.

- 2) Infinite input resistance. That is $R_i = \infty$.
- 3) Zero output resistance. That is $R_o = 0$.
- 4) Zero output voltage when input voltage is zero.
- 5) Infinite bandwidth.
- 6) Infinite common-mode rejection ratio (CMRR). That is $CMRR = \infty$.
- 7) Infinite slew rate.

The measured parameters of an OP-AMP in our research and study are the input bias current and the input offset current.

The input offset current is the algebraic difference between the currents that flow into the inverting and non-inverting terminals of an OP-AMP (Raj Kamal, 2007).

The input bias current is the average of the currents that flow into the inverting and non-inverting terminals of an OP-AMP (Raj Kamal, 2007).

METHODOLOGY

The basic principle of the measuring system reported here incorporates generation of a voltage signal corresponding to the input bias and input off-set currents respectively. This signal is fed to the μP through various interfacing circuits. Suitable programming of the μP , measures and displays the exact values of these currents.

SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

Basically, every dedicated instrument involves hardware and software parts. The design of each of them is presented as follows.

The hardware involves the designs of circuits, relay drive, buffer amplifier, input bias current (I_b) and off-set current (I_{ios}) measuring units. The software consists of initialization, service, calculation and display subroutines. Use of software in assembly language displays the exact value of the measured parameter on the μP display panel. The instrument is software-controlled in such a way that it enables easier modification and allows implementation of complex control functions like selection and sorting of operational amplifiers.

HARDWARE DESIGN

Fig. 2 shows the hardware adopted. The output signal, proportional to the parameter being measured, from I_b and I_{ios} measuring units, is fed to the microprocessor 8088 through a buffer amplifier circuit and analogue-to-digital converter (ADC-0809). It consists of designing of input bias current and offset current measuring units and buffer circuits (Sawhney, *et al*, 2007-2009).

Input Bias Current Measuring Circuit:

The unit designed for measuring input bias current which can be designed as the average of two input bias currents $I_b(-)$ and $I_b(+)$ at both inputs inverting and non-inverting terminals of an OP-AMP. Relations used for I_b are:

Gain of the given circuit = $R_f/R_i = 100k/100 = 1000$;

$$\begin{aligned} I_b &= I_1 + I_2 \\ I_1 &= 0 \text{ and } I_2 = V_o(\text{bias})/R_2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Therefore,

$$I_b = I_2 = V_o(\text{bias})/R_2 = 0.056V/100k = 560 \text{ nA.}$$

As it can be clearly seen, I_b varies from 100 nA to 1 μA (Towers, *et al*, 2006).

POINT 7: + 12 VOLTS
 POINT 4: - 12 VOLTS
 Fig. 2: The Complete Circuit.

UL: UPPER LIMIT
 LL: LOWER LIMIT

Fig. 3: Generalised Flow Chart For Measuring The Input Current Parameters Of The OP-AMP.

Input Off-Set Current Measuring Unit:

Input off-set current is an indicator of degree of mismatching between two bias currents and is a measure of matching of input-stage transistor pair. It is a temperature-sensitive specification of an OP-AMP and changes with time. The mathematical relations involved are:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{ios} &= I_b (+) - I_b (-); \\ \text{Gain of OP-AMP} &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$I_b (+) = V_o/R_1 = 125 \text{ V}/1.656 \text{ M} = 75.48 \text{ nA}$, when S1 is open.

$I_b (-) = -V_o/R_2 = 31.2 \text{ mV}/1.656 \text{ M} = 18.84 \text{ nA}$, when S2 is open.

$I_{ios} = 75.48 - 18.84 = 56.64 \text{ nA}$.

I_{ios} varies from 30 nA to 200 nA, from our research and measurements.

SOFTWARE DESIGN

In the software design (figure 3), firstly, the system is initialized. After delay, the A/D card is read and stored in memory M. This memory is compared with upper limit and lower limit under different conditions; either Over Range or Under Range is displayed, otherwise, the exact value of the parameter is displayed on μP output panel, when calculation subroutine is called.

CONCLUSION

This dedicated instrument is very fast in operation and gives the exact values of I_b and I_{ios} of OP-AMP, one after the other. Both these parameters are temperature-sensitive specifications of an OP-AMP. Input off-set current value is always smaller than that of input bias current. A number of OP-AMPs of same design have different values of the above parameters. Several OP-AMPs have been tested and this measuring system yields satisfactory results. Efforts are being directed towards designing circuits that would measure other parameters of linear integrated circuits using similar techniques. The maximum percentage error in the measurements of the input bias-offset currents of the operational amplifier using the measurement system was found to be 1.5 %.

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Received for Publication: 30/04/10

Accepted for Publication: 12/06/10

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